

A Formal Account for Reasoning About Uncertain Probabilities in Intelligence Analysis

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Abstract—In the sixth assessment of the international panel on climate change (IPCC) one can read sentences such as “cumulative net CO2 emissions over the last decade (2010-2019) are about the same size as the 11 remaining carbon budget *likely* to limit warming to 1.5C (*medium confidence*).” Such reports are very common in the intelligence community, but a formal account for dealing with the degree of belief and of confidence is still missing. In this paper, we propose a formal account for allowing such degrees of belief and the associated confidence to be used to label arguments in abstract argumentation settings. We focus on the task of probabilistic inference over a chosen query building upon Sato’s distribution semantics which has been already shown to encompass a variety of cases including the semantics of Bayesian networks. Borrowing from the vast literature on such semantics, we examine how such tasks can be dealt with in practice when considering uncertain probabilities.

Index Terms—uncertain probabilities, intelligence analysis, artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

In the sixth assessment of the international panel on climate change (IPCC), one can read sentences such as “cumulative net CO2 emissions over the last decade (2010-2019) are about the same size as the 11 remaining carbon budget *likely* to limit warming to 1.5C (*medium confidence*)” [1, p. TS-16]. Reports using similar labels for expressing the degrees of belief and confidence are common in intelligence analysis, but a formal account for dealing with them is still missing.

Such expressions of uncertainty refer to two different notions of uncertainty: *aleatory* (or *aleatoric*), and *epistemic* uncertainty [2]. Aleatory uncertainty refers to the variability in the outcome of an experiment which is due to inherently random effects (*e.g.*, flipping a fair coin): no additional source of information but Laplace’s daemon¹ can reduce such variability. Epistemic uncertainty refers to the epistemic state of the agent using the model, hence its lack of knowledge that—

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¹“An intelligence that, at a given instant, could comprehend all the forces by which nature is animated and the respective situation of the beings that make it up” [3, p.2].

in principle—can be reduced based on additional data samples (*e.g.*, being in the position to assess whether a coin is fair or not requires trials).

Beta distributions (Section II-A) can be used to represent such expressions of uncertainty formally [4, p. 49]. They provide a compact representation of both aleatory and epistemic uncertainty when dealing with binary variables [5].

An intelligence analysis report is a structured, logical statement that conveys insightful conclusions and recommendations from systematically evaluating information and data, each with its estimated epistemic and aleatory uncertainty levels. Most of the community’s efforts to support such an evaluation of information and data focused on Bayesian networks and probabilistic logic programming under distribution semantics [6], [7], which we will illustrate in the form of algebraic model counting [8] (Section II-B). In particular, [9] looks at aleatory and epistemic uncertainty propagation in singly-connected Bayesian networks; [10] provides efficient mechanisms for embedding aleatory and epistemic uncertainty in probabilistic logic programs; and finally [11] generalises the approach considering probabilistic circuits.

The insightful conclusions in an intelligence analysis report hardly need to be fully in agreement. Showing conflicting conclusions in intelligence analysis is valuable when alternative explanations exist, biases must be addressed, and a more holistic understanding is necessary. It supports transparency, objectivity, and critical thinking. Formal argumentation theory [12] is a recent endeavour in the artificial intelligence community to provide rigorous reasoning with conflicting information. It provides criteria for determining which conflicting arguments can rationally stand together and form a coherent position.

In this paper, we introduce the distribution semantics in abstract argumentation (Section III) at first considering only probabilities. We then show how the very same semantics can handle beta distributions by leveraging recent work on probabilistic circuits [11]. Section IV pencils in a series of related research questions that this line of research should address, while Section V concludes the paper.

II. BACKGROUND

Scientific assessments of complex phenomena [13] require to consider not only their likelihood but also the overall confidence in the exercise. Let us suppose we know there is a

coin that can be flipped, and a source of information is telling us that it is unlikely with low confidence that it will land on the head. This is a way to express uncertain probabilities, for instance, because of limited observations: just observing a few times a coin flipping we can only have a low confidence on whether the coin is fair or not.

A. Beta Distributions

Epistemic and aleatory uncertainty can be jointly captured by a beta distribution, namely a distribution of possible probabilities. When facing a phenomenon with just two outcomes a *complete dataset* \mathcal{D} is a sequence (allowing for repetitions) of examples, each being a vector of instantiations of independent Bernoulli distributions with true but unknown parameter π . From this, the *likelihood* is thus: $p(\mathcal{D} \mid \pi) = \prod_{n=1}^{|\mathcal{D}|} p(x_n \mid \pi) = \prod_{n=1}^N \pi^{x_n} (1 - \pi)^{1-x_n}$ where x_i represents the i -th example in the dataset \mathcal{D} , which is assumed to hold either the value 1 or 0.

To develop a Bayesian analysis of the phenomenon, we can choose as prior the beta distribution, with parameters $\alpha = \langle \alpha_x, \alpha_{\bar{x}} \rangle$, $\alpha_x > 0$ and $\alpha_{\bar{x}} > 0$, that is conjugate to the Bernoulli: $\text{Beta}(\pi \mid \alpha) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha_x + \alpha_{\bar{x}})}{\Gamma(\alpha_x)\Gamma(\alpha_{\bar{x}})} \pi^{\alpha_x - 1} (1 - \pi)^{\alpha_{\bar{x}} - 1}$ where $\Gamma(t) \equiv \int_0^\infty u^{t-1} e^{-u} du$ is the *gamma* function.

Considering a beta distributed prior $\text{Beta}(\pi \mid \alpha^0)$ and the Bernoulli likelihood function, and given $|\mathcal{D}|$ observations $\mathbf{m} = \langle m_x, m_{\bar{x}} \rangle$ of x , *viz.* m_x observations of $x = 1$, $m_{\bar{x}}$ observations of $x = 0$, and $m_x + m_{\bar{x}} = |\mathcal{D}|$: $p(\pi \mid \mathcal{D}, \alpha^0) = \text{Beta}(\pi \mid \alpha^0 + \mathbf{m})$.

Thus, the parameters of a beta distribution can be considered pseudocounts [14] of *pieces of evidence* for the two outcomes of a phenomenon, and the beta distribution itself can be seen as a representation of the uncertain probability associated with the phenomenon. Among the various priors, using $\alpha^0 = \mathbf{1} = \langle 1, 1 \rangle$ is equivalent to using the uniform distribution, which represents a non-informative prior that maximises entropy.

Given a beta-distributed random variable X , $s_X = \alpha_x + \alpha_{\bar{x}}$ is its *Dirichlet strength* and $\mu_X = \frac{\alpha_x}{s_X}$ is its mean, which relates to the *aleatory uncertainty*. The variance of a beta-distributed random variable — which associates to the *epistemic uncertainty* — X is $\sigma_X^2 = \frac{\mu_X(1-\mu_X)}{s_X+1}$.

Following [4, p. 49] we can represent fuzzy labels² such as *likely* with *low confidence* by means of beta distributions, by associating the first label to ranges of expected values (aleatory uncertainty) and the latter to ranges of variance values (epistemic uncertainty): the lower the confidence, the higher the variance. For instance, a proposition that is *likely* true with *some confidence* could be associated with a beta distribution $\text{Beta}(5.00, 1.50)$ as its expected value (0.7692) sits at the centre of the chosen range of values for the fuzzy label *likely*, and analogously the variance (0.0237) for the fuzzy label *some confidence*.

²The list of fuzzy labels for aleatory uncertainty is [4, p. 49]: *absolutely not likely, very unlikely, unlikely, somewhat unlikely, chances about even, somewhat likely, likely, very likely, absolutely likely*. The list of fuzzy labels for epistemic uncertainty is [4, p. 49]: *no confidence, low confidence, some confidence, high confidence, total confidence*.

B. Logical Reasoning with Beta Distributions

In [11] the authors provide a formal account for reasoning over probabilistic circuits which can be derived from propositional theories through knowledge compilation. In this setting, probabilistic inference is a special case of algebraic model counting (AMC) [8], which generalises weighted model counting (WMC) to the semiring setting and supports various types of labels, including numerical ones as used in WMC, but also sets, polynomials, Boolean formulae, and many more. The underlying mathematical structure is that of a commutative semiring.

A *semiring* is a structure $\langle \mathcal{A}, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes \rangle$, where *addition* \oplus and *multiplication* \otimes are associative binary operations over the set \mathcal{A} , \oplus is commutative, \otimes distributes over \oplus , $e^\oplus \in \mathcal{A}$ is the neutral element of \oplus , $e^\otimes \in \mathcal{A}$ that of \otimes , and for all $a \in \mathcal{A}$, $e^\oplus \otimes a = a \otimes e^\oplus = e^\oplus$. In a *commutative semiring*, \otimes is commutative as well.

Algebraic model counting is now defined [8] as follows. Given: a *propositional logic theory* T over a set of variables \mathcal{V} , a *commutative semiring* $\langle \mathcal{A}, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes \rangle$, and a *labelling function* $\rho: \mathcal{L} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$, mapping literals \mathcal{L} of the variables in \mathcal{V} to elements of the semiring set \mathcal{A} , compute

$$\mathbf{A}(T) = \bigoplus_{I \in \mathcal{M}(T)} \bigotimes_{l \in I} \rho(l), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{M}(T)$ denotes the set of models of T .

1) *Probabilistic Inferences*: Among others, AMC generalises the task of probabilistic inference according to [6]’s semantics (**PROB**), [8, Thm. 1]. A *query* q is a finite set of algebraic literals $q \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. We denote the set of interpretations where the query is true by $\mathcal{I}(q)$,

$$\mathcal{I}(q) = \{I \mid I \in \mathcal{M}(T) \wedge q \subseteq I\} \quad (2)$$

The label of a query q is defined³ as the label of $\mathcal{I}(q)$,

$$\mathbf{A}(q) = \mathbf{A}(\mathcal{I}(q)) = \bigoplus_{I \in \mathcal{I}(q)} \bigotimes_{l \in I} \rho(l). \quad (3)$$

As both operators are commutative and associative, the label is independent of the order of both literals and interpretations.

In the case of probabilities as labels, *i.e.*, $\rho(\cdot) \in [0, 1]$, Eq. (4) presents the AMC parametrisation for handling **PROB** of queries:

$$\begin{array}{lll} \mathcal{A} = \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} & a \oplus b = a + b & a \otimes b = a \cdot b \\ e^\oplus = 0 & e^\otimes = 1 & \rho(\neg f) = 1 - \rho(f) \end{array} \quad (4)$$

A naïve implementation of Eq. (1) is clearly exponential: [15] introduced the first method for deriving tractable circuits (d-DNNFs) that allow polytime algorithms for clausal entailment, model counting and enumeration. In particular, we can exploit the succinctness results of the knowledge compilation map by [16], where an overview of succinctness relationships between various types of circuits are provided. Instead of

³Albeit \mathbf{A} has been introduced to operate over propositional logic theories, with a small abuse of notation we use it also for a finite set of literals, *i.e.*, *query*, and a set of interpretations.

Algorithm 1 Evaluating an NNF circuit N for a commutative semiring $(\mathcal{A}, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes)$ and labelling function ρ .

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1: procedure EVAL( $N, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes, \rho$ )
2:   if  $N$  is a true node  $\top$  then return  $e^\otimes$ 
3:   if  $N$  is a false node  $\perp$  then return  $e^\oplus$ 
4:   if  $N$  is a literal node  $l$  then return  $\rho(l)$ 
5:   if  $N$  is a disjunction  $\bigvee_{i=1}^m N_i$  then
6:     return  $\bigoplus_{i=1}^m \text{EVAL}(N_i, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes, \rho)$ 
7:   if  $N$  is a conjunction  $\bigwedge_{i=1}^m N_i$  then
8:     return  $\bigotimes_{i=1}^m \text{EVAL}(N_i, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes, \rho)$ 

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focusing on classical, flat target compilation languages based on conjunctive or disjunctive normal forms, [16] considers a richer, nested class based on representing propositional sentences using directed acyclic graphs: NNFs. A sentence in *negation normal form* (NNF) over a set of propositional variables \mathcal{V} is a rooted, directed acyclic graph where each leaf node is labelled with true (\top), false (\perp), or a literal of a variable in \mathcal{V} , and each internal node with disjunction (\vee) or conjunction (\wedge).

An NNF is *decomposable* if for each conjunction node $\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \phi_i$, no two children ϕ_i and ϕ_j share any variable. An NNF is *deterministic* if for each disjunction node $\bigvee_{i=1}^n \phi_i$, each pair of different children ϕ_i and ϕ_j are logically contradictory, that is $\phi_i \wedge \phi_j \models \perp$ for $i \neq j$. In other terms, only one child can be true at any time. An NNF is *smooth* when $\text{vars}(\phi_i) = \text{vars}(\phi_j)$ for any two children ϕ_i and ϕ_j of a disjunction node, where $\text{vars}(x)$ denotes all propositional variables that appear in the subgraph are rooted at x .

The function EVAL specified in Algorithm 1 *evaluates* an NNF circuit for a commutative semiring $(\mathcal{A}, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes)$ and labelling function ρ . Evaluating an NNF representation N_T of a propositional theory T for a semiring $(\mathcal{A}, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes)$ and labelling function ρ is a *sound AMC computation* iff $\text{EVAL}(N_T, \oplus, \otimes, e^\oplus, e^\otimes, \rho) = \mathbf{A}(T)$.

Following the intuition in [17], the same circuit can be reused for multiple queries. For instance, from Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), the very same circuit used for computing $\mathbf{A}(T)$ can be used for computing the probability of a query q by enforcing that the leaf associated to $\neg q$ carries no weight in the final computation. For further details, see [7], [17].

2) *Inferences with Beta Distributions*: To use beta distributions as labels, in [11], the authors provide operators that expand on Eq. (4) for what concerns expected values of the random variables and approximate the resulting variance using Taylor approximations. They require as input also the matrix of covariance between such random variables, which captures their second-order dependencies. In their proposal, e^\oplus is a beta distribution with an expected value of 0 and null variance. e^\otimes is a beta distribution with an expected value of 1 and null 0.

Looking at Algorithm 1, there is the need to introduce specific operators for \bigoplus and \bigotimes , which are used when facing a disjunction or a conjunction node. In the case of a disjunction n over C nodes — its children — the operators

proposed in [11] return a beta distribution whose expected value is the sum of the expected values of its children, hence $\mathbb{E}[X_n] = \sum_{c \in C} \mathbb{E}[X_c]$. In the case of a conjunction, the operator returns a beta distribution whose expected value is approximated to the product of the expected values of its children, $\mathbb{E}[X_n] \simeq \Pi(\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{X}_C])$, as it results from a Taylor approximation. The operators proposed in [11] also try to faithfully approximate the variance of the resulting beta distributions, for both disjunction and conjunction nodes, by manipulating the covariances between each of their children and the other nodes in the circuit.

III. UNCERTAINTY AND CONFLICTING CONCLUSIONS

In Section II, we briefly recalled techniques for reasoning about epistemic and aleatory uncertainty represented through beta distributions. We now turn our attention to the issue of supporting argumentative-probabilistic reasoning.

A. Background in Abstract Argumentation

An *argumentation framework* (AF) [18] is a pair $\Gamma = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$ where \mathcal{A} is a set of arguments and $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}$. We say that \mathbf{b} *attacks* \mathbf{a} iff $\langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a} \rangle \in \mathcal{R}$, also denoted as $\mathbf{b} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}$. The set of attackers of an argument \mathbf{a} is denoted as $\mathbf{a}^- \triangleq \{\mathbf{b} : \mathbf{b} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}\}$, the set of arguments attacked by \mathbf{a} is denoted as $\mathbf{a}^+ \triangleq \{\mathbf{b} : \mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}\}$. Analogously, we can define the set of arguments attacked by a set of arguments $E \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ as $E^+ \triangleq \{\mathbf{b} \mid \exists \mathbf{a} \in E, \mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}\}$.

The basic properties of conflict-freeness, acceptability, and admissibility of a set of arguments are fundamental for the definition of argumentation semantics. Given an AF $\Gamma = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$:

- a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is a *conflict-free* set of Γ if $\nexists \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in S$ s.t. $\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}$;
- an argument $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$ is *acceptable* in Γ with respect to a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ if $\forall \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A}$ s.t. $\mathbf{b} \rightarrow \mathbf{a}$, $\exists \mathbf{c} \in S$ s.t. $\mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{b}$;
- the function $\mathcal{F}_\Gamma : 2^{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\mathcal{F}_\Gamma(S) = \{\mathbf{a} \mid \mathbf{a} \text{ is acceptable in } \Gamma \text{ w.r.t. } S\}$ is called the *characteristic function* of Γ .

An argumentation semantics σ prescribes for any AF Γ a set of *extensions*, denoted as $\mathcal{E}_\sigma(\Gamma)$, i.e., a set of sets of arguments satisfying the conditions dictated by σ . Given an AF $\Gamma = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$, a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ is:

- an *admissible extension* of Γ , i.e. $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{AD}}(\Gamma)$, iff S is an admissible set of Γ , i.e. $S \subseteq \mathcal{F}_\Gamma(S)$;
- a *complete extension* of Γ , i.e. $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{CO}}(\Gamma)$, iff $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{CF}}(\Gamma)$ and $S = \mathcal{F}_\Gamma(S)$;
- the *grounded extension* of Γ , i.e. $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{GR}}(\Gamma)$, iff S is the minimal (w.r.t. set inclusion) complete extension of Γ ;
- a *stable extension* of Γ , i.e. $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{ST}}(\Gamma)$, iff S is a conflict-free set of Γ and $S \cup S^+ = \mathcal{A}$;
- a *preferred extension* of Γ , i.e. $S \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{PR}}(\Gamma)$, iff S is a maximal (w.r.t. set inclusion) admissible set of Γ .

Given an argumentation framework Γ , an argument \mathbf{a} , and a semantics σ , \mathbf{a} is said to be *credulously accepted* according to σ if $\exists S \in \mathcal{E}_\sigma(\Gamma)$ such that $\mathbf{a} \in S$.

In the following, we make use of the fact that given an argumentation framework Γ and a semantics σ , it is possible

to derive a propositional theory whose models are $\mathcal{E}_\sigma(\Gamma)$. For instance, from [19] an argumentation framework can be transformed into a propositional theory whose models are isomorphic to the admissible sets. In particular, from [19, Prop. 6], such a formula can be:

$$\bigwedge_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}} \left(\left(\mathbf{a} \supset \bigwedge_{\mathbf{b} \in \{\mathbf{a}\}^-} \neg \mathbf{b} \right) \wedge \left(\mathbf{a} \supset \bigwedge_{\mathbf{b} \in \{\mathbf{a}\}^-} \bigvee_{\mathbf{c} \in \{\mathbf{b}\}^-} \mathbf{c} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

Given an argumentation framework Γ and a semantics σ , let us denote with $\Phi(\Gamma, \sigma)$ an arbitrary propositional theory whose models are isomorphic to $\mathcal{E}_\Gamma(\sigma)$. Please note that we do not claim that such a theory can always be derived in polynomial time from the definition of the argumentation framework.

To illustrate our proposal, let us consider the following running example loosely connected to the IPCC sixth's assessment [1, p. TS-16] (*cf.*, Section I).

Example 1. Let consider the argument \mathbf{d} stating that “from the collected evidence, we conclude that cumulative net CO2 emissions over the last decade (2010-2019) are about the same size as the 11 remaining carbon budget to limit warming to 1.5C.” Let us assume that such a conclusion involved assessing three further arguments, thus giving rise to the $\Gamma_E = \langle \mathcal{A}_E, \mathcal{R}_E \rangle$ argumentation framework where $\mathcal{A}_E = \{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{d}\}$ and $\mathcal{R}_E = \{\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{b} \rightarrow \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c} \rightarrow \mathbf{d}\}$. Given the sensitivity and complexity of the topic, we refrain from instantiating such additional arguments with natural language text for avoiding unnecessary debate over what should be just an illustrative example.

From Eq. (5), $\Phi(\Gamma_E, \text{AD}) = (\mathbf{c} \supset (\neg \mathbf{a})) \wedge (\mathbf{c} \supset (\neg \mathbf{b})) \wedge (\mathbf{d} \supset (\mathbf{a} \vee \mathbf{b})) \wedge (\neg \mathbf{c}) \equiv (\neg \mathbf{c}) \wedge (\mathbf{d} \supset (\mathbf{a} \vee \mathbf{b}))$.

B. Algebraic Model Counting and Abstract Argumentation

Prior to the case of uncertain probabilities represented through beta distributions, let us discuss probabilistic inferences over argumentation frameworks considering simple probabilities, *i.e.*, the setting illustrated in Eq. (4).

A *probabilistic graph* is a tuple $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \rho \rangle$ where $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$ is an abstract argumentation framework and $\rho : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow [0, 1]$. Given a probabilistic graph $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \rho \rangle$ and a set of arguments $S \subseteq \mathcal{A}$, the probability of such a set of arguments is:

$$\rho(S) = \bigotimes_{\mathbf{a} \in S} \rho(\mathbf{a}) \otimes \bigotimes_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A} \setminus S} \overline{\rho(\mathbf{a})} \quad (6)$$

Let us introduce the probabilistic inference according to [6]’s semantics of a queried argument \mathbf{a} as the sum of the probabilities of σ ’s extensions in which \mathbf{a} is present.⁴

Definition 1. Given a probabilistic graph $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \rho \rangle$ over an argumentation framework $\Gamma = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$, an argument $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$, and a semantics $\sigma \in \{\text{CF}, \text{AD}, \text{CO}, \text{GR}, \text{ST}, \text{PR}\}$,

$$\mathbf{PROB}(\mathbf{a}, \sigma, \Gamma) = \bigoplus_{\{E \in \mathcal{E}_\sigma(\Gamma) \mid \mathbf{a} \in E\}} \rho(E). \quad (7)$$

⁴Definition 1 generalises the semantics provided in [20], where the authors restrict to the CF case only.

TABLE I: Probabilistic inferences over Γ_E , with chosen $\rho(q)$ labels, using Definition 1.

q	$\rho(q)$	$\mathbf{PROB}(q, \text{AD}, \Gamma_E)$
a	Beta(1.00, 1.00) <i>Chances about even with no confidence</i>	Beta(1.35, 2.07) <i>Somewhat unlikely with low confidence</i>
b	Beta(17.00, 2.00) <i>Very likely with high confidence</i>	Beta(14.57, 6.06) <i>Likely with high confidence</i>
c	Beta(4.00, 15.00) <i>Unlikely with high confidence</i>	Beta(1.00, $+\infty$) <i>Absolutely not likely with total confidence</i>
d	Beta(5.00, 1.50) <i>Likely with some confidence</i>	Beta(7.05, 5.21) <i>Somewhat likely with some confidence</i>

We can now demonstrate—we omit the proofs due to space constraints—that $\mathbf{PROB}(\mathbf{a}, \sigma, \Gamma)$ is an instance of AMC.

Theorem 1. Given a probabilistic graph $\langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R}, \rho \rangle$ over an argumentation framework $\Gamma = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$, and given $\mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}$, AMC generalises $\mathbf{PROB}(\mathbf{a}, \sigma, \Gamma)$.

C. Argumentative Reasoning over Beta Distributions

Let us consider our running example (Example 1) again and let us suppose to label arguments with the beta distributions⁵ as listed in the second column of Table I. Table I also shows the results of probabilistic inferences over Γ_E when considering Definition 1 using AD as argumentation semantics, and the machinery provided by [11], recalled in Section II-B2.

From inspection of the results, the knowledge we inject through the structure of the argumentation graph heavily affects the result of the probabilistic query. Because there is no admissible extension in which \mathbf{c} is accepted, its probabilistic assessment is *absolutely not likely with total confidence* (equivalent to e^\oplus). Moreover, the probabilistic assessment of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} considers that admissible sets are not complete; hence there are cases where only one of the two (alternating) is in such a set. Finally, we began our example from \mathbf{d} and its uncertainty assessment as *likely with some confidence*, and post-hoc, we assumed both Γ_E as an argumentation graph representing our understanding of the relationships between possible relevant arguments, and the labels listed in the second column of Table I which complete the label for \mathbf{d} we already had. Such assumptions affect \mathbf{d} , which now becomes *somewhat likely with some confidence*. The aleatory evaluation of \mathbf{d} has been affected by the uncanny uninformative $\rho(\mathbf{a})$, despite being unattacked in Γ_E . In future work, we will characterise possible *rationality constraints* building upon the extensive literature on epistemic approach to probabilistic argumentation [22] and ranking semantics, *e.g.*, [23]. \mathbf{PROB} can thus become a useful test for assessing the consistency of both probabilistic assessments and the logical dependencies between arguments.

⁵In [21], the authors also label arguments with beta distributions in the form of subjective logic opinions [4] for representing their level of trust.

IV. DISCUSSION

The paper provides some primary preliminary results which may enable further developments and raises more questions than provides solutions. First, there is an underlying independence assumption between the probabilistic labels associated with each argument, e.g., $\rho(\mathbf{a} \mid \mathbf{b}) = \rho(\mathbf{a})$ for any \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} . On the one hand, this is unrealistic: there is always the possibility of having confounding variables. At the same time, experimental analysis on synthetic data [24] shows that dependencies often do not change significantly in a probabilistic assessment. Deciding whether the independence assumption between random variables is reasonable appears thus to be debatable, and it should be represented in an argumentative appraisal of a phenomenon, thus adding a meta-level.

Definition 1 can also be seen as a way to *weight* argumentation extensions. From this perspective, it goes in the direction presented, for instance, in [25, § 3.2] and [26, § 3]. While we focus on supporting probabilistic reasoning, we will analyse the connection further in future work.

In this paper, we limited ourselves to consider labels for arguments only. We, however, can think of extending the approach considering uncertain probabilities labelling for attacks, too, thanks to formal results provided in [27]. In that paper, the authors introduced the argumentation framework with recursive attacks and, among other results, [27, Def. 19] shows how to represent attacks as arguments while ensuring [27, Prop. 6–12] semantic correspondence.

Finally, given the connection between probabilistic inferences and Bayesian networks [17], an interesting future research question concerns the syntactic relationship — if possible — between Bayesian networks with binary random variables and argumentation frameworks which ensures semantic correspondence too.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we show a machinery for the effective evaluation of argumentation frameworks with both epistemic and aleatory uncertainty, represented through beta distributions used in intelligence analysis and scientific assessments. In particular, we focused on the machinery provided by (algebraic) model counting, which led us to introduce a novel probabilistic evaluation (**PROB**, Definition 1). We nevertheless show how both probabilistic evaluations are instances of the model counting problem, and illustrate their difference in our running example.

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